

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATION , ICT AND COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14563780

Ana Paula Silva dos Santos Ramalho

*Pedagogy teacher at the State Secretariat of Education of Espírito Santo – SEDU.
Postgraduate student strictu sensu (Master's degree), at the Vale do Cricaré University
Center – São Mateus (ES). E-mail: anapaularamalhosdj@gmail.com*

Maria Nazaré Ribon Silva

*Graduated in Portuguese Language and Literature. Master in Education from the IPLAC
Institute - Cuba. Psychopedagogue. Teacher of Specialized Educational Services. E-mail:
nazareribonsilva@hotmail.com*

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*Educator. Post-Doctorate in Psychology. Researcher. Scientific Consultant. E-mail:
srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.*

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of the relationship between education, ICTs and cognitive development. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it discusses a topic that crosses contemporary educational paradigms and its condition for changing behavior and thinking. Its social relevance lies in clarifying to the general public the possibilities, potentialities and challenges that arise through the insertion of ICTs in formal school environments. This is a bibliographical research, based on the interpretation and broad discussion of the topic by the authors, given their respective backgrounds in human and social sciences. Cognitive development is a sociological and individual condition that is formed and consolidated through experience and its analysis, interpretation and understanding until it is synthesized. Intellectual advances cannot be attributed solely by linking this category to the use of tools that quickly obtain objective answers from the user and that, over time, interferes in their subjectivity, transforming them into a slave to that which was supposed to be an exponential promoter of their condition of epistemic freedom. In the same way, intellectuality can only be achieved as a form of recognition by the group to which one belongs, when one produces something of such relevance that it proves capable of influencing and changing, for the better, the lives of the participants; it is not a schizopathic thought that applies to oneself and that finds recognition through views and followers, who are as ignorant or even more ignorant than the content producer. It is important to clarify that modern technology tools are the product of intense

research; they did not result from hasty ideas lacking logical foundations, especially because they were created to serve specific groups that dealt with issues of the highest relevance, such as national security for the respective countries from which they originated.

Keywords: Education and Information Technologies. Education. Cognitive development. Intellectuality.

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive development can only be achieved through experience, because it allows the individual to compile the situation, creating a synthesis and, by storing the entire process in his memory, on any other occasion that is stimulated in that sense, the brain itself will take care of make comparisons and a path already taken is highlighted, making the action to confront the problem less complex. With the emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and their consequent indexation to the educational system, as part of the political *lobby*, all types of prediction for the future was made, promising miracles in learning.

The propaganda that was and still is made about technology is much greater than the direct harm it causes; because total ignorance is even less worse than *scientific guesswork*, a feeling that has taken over a range of individuals who, because they are connected to the network and have access to an impressive range of content, feel they have the right to label themselves as thinkers, geniuses and intellectuals.

Here, we must clarify another issue, which is intellectuality, which can only be achieved as a form of recognition by the group to which one belongs; it is not a schizopathic thought that applies to oneself and finds recognition through views and followers, who are as ignorant or even more ignorant than the content producer. This arose because humanity was driven to enter an era in which it is easier, when faced with a highly complex subject, to seek the opinion of some [*supposed*] scholar and then repeat it, as if it represented the supreme truth, if not the only one. In this process of validating knowledge by brute intellectual force, a type of idiot is being produced that is the most dangerous for society, the one who has a voice and followers, disciples, who follow him and his ideas without questioning their objective value and their impact on objective reality. The simple fact that one is being repeated in one's nonsense is already reason to be interpreted as intellectual.

With ICTs, it has become even easier for those who are too lazy to think or who cannot even make such a mnemonic effort, because the reproduction of ideas can be done by pressing a button, without even having to read the text to learn the facts. In the past, this individual would

have to write a short text and submit it to a journal so that it could be analyzed and then made available to the public. Now, everything is free, which makes many say that the *Internet* is a lawless land and, it should be added..., without order, without parameters.

Everything that emerges is immediately treated as something new, and when someone takes a stand to seek a deeper understanding of what is happening, they are immediately treated as a retrograde, as a mortal enemy of progress, and this figure must be fought *with forceps* . Any data presented [*in favor, of course*] is treated as fact, and questioning it is treated as an affront.

It should be clarified that modern technology tools are the product of intense research; they did not result from hasty ideas lacking logical foundations, especially because they were created to serve specific groups that dealt with issues of the highest relevance, such as national security for the respective countries from which they originated.

When they were first conceived, the goal was that only people with a high intellectual level would use these tools; for this simple reason, their barriers were shown to be [*almost*] non-existent; the interest was that information would circulate at a speed that would not hinder decision-making at high levels of command. However, by making them freely available, an atomic bomb was placed in the hands of people without [*much*] character and who do not care to think about the firepower that lies within their respective powers. In this regard, a whole set of preventive actions and measures, with high contingency, were and continue to be neglected.

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND INTELLECTUAL-COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT

ICTs have invaded everyone's private and social lives without even giving them the opportunity to discuss how this advancement would occur, how it would be incorporated into everyday life, which could not stop to receive a primer indicating good usage practices, a manual that would respond to everyone's anxieties and fears. One thing cannot be ignored, which is an in-depth analysis of how these technologies have influenced the behavior of individuals, creating new ways of being and thinking about objective and subjective reality, sometimes experiencing a potential never seen [*or even thought of*] in any other political moment of human civilization, sometimes overwhelming humans to the limit of subservience and pathological dependence.

Thus, what is being discussed is the conditions for using ICTs that are available to the general population. The productive potential that they have shown is indisputable; however,

there is a clash over the cognitive and intellectual potential of those who have access to them. The lack of preparation of students and most teachers to address the maximum possible scope of their respective uses goes beyond and conflicts with the interest in transforming them into an instrument of erudite research that can radically change the lives of individuals and nations.

If its action is geared towards a sustainability project, this would make the lives of most humans more equitable. Unfortunately, its implementation has been treated at the level of common sense, as if individuals were not able to develop their intellects in accordance with the development of the process of human cultural capital that has been accumulated over centuries and that has served as the basis for the research that culminated in the contemporary technological revolution.

With the technologies implemented, we do not hear a different discourse, in which most of them refer to the issue of optimized time with the use of new work tools, which led to an increase in social inequality, because it ended up generating a new type of exclusion, the so-called digital exclusion.

The objective, with technology, is to make life more comprehensive, more fluid, in the sense of allowing greater availability of space and time for leisure and coexistence, which has occurred in the opposite way; because, the more opportunities for flexibility applied to the conditions of freedom, the more enslaved everyone has become, trapped in attitudes that do nothing more than exalt the individual ego and bring nothing as a benefit to practical reason.

Information and communication technology, if placed outside the context of the constant search for human personal development through a concrete sense of being, ends up becoming a monster that enslaves its prey, because this is all that human beings become, especially teachers and students within the teaching and learning process itself, reducing all thought to random combinations of things devoid of any causal connection with empirical reality. Thought and the act of thinking become unnecessary, because there is the illusory possibility that machines will provide the objective answer, optimizing the process and shortening the time lapse between the idea and its realization.

ICTs represent an enigma for this moment and need to be interpreted and understood, with the purpose of enabling students to take advantage of their potential, achieving significant gains in the fields of knowledge. This understanding inevitably leads to an understanding of how well and how poorly they are available and what care should be taken when using such instruments.

The technological revolution has brought a serious problem to education, which is having to 'adapt' to this new reality and fight against illiteracy and digital exclusion. The

responsibility of schools and teachers is in the same proportion as that maintained in favor of literacy and graphic literacy. However, the fight was unequal, as they were given three functions and no intellectual support apparatus; after all, there is no way for schools to engender it in their curriculum if their agents either ignore the new technology or [even] manage to resist it. The technological revolution is still in its infancy in a world increasingly concerned with how to achieve the humanistic formation of the individual and, since schools are the product of a culture and time that are unique in their forms and approaches, it is up to them to seek to overcome this culture, to mold it into a humanistic structure so that they can then apply it in its entirety. It is obvious that, given the speed at which technological advances are arriving and being imposed on everyone, without distinction, *no one will be offered* an environment similar to the present one or with only slight modifications. It will have to be radically different from everything that has been known up until now. Therefore, the role of teachers, as guardians of the past, must change, because their backward-looking orientation is inapplicable to present and future purposes, which demands a fundamental readjustment of the didactic and methodological political proposal.

The search for an intermediate categorical position between the total subordination of modern science to technological, economic and political objectives, on the one hand, and the total independence of science, on the other, has led to attempts to establish more rational criteria for the distribution of resources between different types of scientific, teaching, learning and extension activities.

The technological revolution is a reality; it has reached schools and an interesting fact is that teachers are often completely unprepared for tasks performed online. Being aware of new market changes has become the order of the day and this can be a major bottleneck to the cognitive and intellectual development of the population, especially students. The use of technologies in education is already an essential reality and it is no longer possible to think of a complete humanistic education without digital inclusion as part of this education ; however, this inclusion must be designed in a way that meets individual and collective desires; not just an impartial and megalomaniac dictatorship.

Even if one wants to question the resistance of a considerable part of the population to the insertion of ICTs as an indispensable condition for a broad experience and interaction with the world in the 21st century, it was this same condition of confrontation and challenge to the new that guaranteed its survival with dignity until the present moment, questioning the validity and integrity of what was made available to it as a magical element.

The arrival of modern technologies could even represent a spectacular advance, as has been shown and proven [*in theory*]; but, in the same way, the initial fear, combined with distrust towards it, proved to be a very useful strategy, as became very clear as soon as its [*almost*] invisible loopholes and ways of stealing confidential data from others without leaving a trace were discovered.

Since its emergence, new forms of attacks on law-abiding citizens have begun to be perpetrated and terrorist acts have been carried out on a large domestic and even global scale. At the same time as it has fostered a drastic change in social thinking, contributing to increasingly broad advances, the lack of instruments to protect against user insecurity had to be invented and developed, so that the general public could be protected against such situations.

Another conflicting situation was the *promise* that machines would replace human beings, even in the simplest and most ridiculous everyday functions, which made those who are always taking risks and in fear, begin to see it as a terrible and monstrous form of domination by the plutocracy against the most defenseless. Even in schools, the situation was no different, because the school curriculum cannot be completely adulterated in the name of an assumption, a delirium about a possible future that was shown to be Hollywood-like catastrophic for all those who were not the magnates of power and with such power to control whoever [*supposedly*] controlled the great mass, that is, it would be the absolute hegemony of the dominant power.

Thus, it was not the emergence of technology and its insertion into the social world that was the major problem that began to haunt society; but the way in which propaganda about it and its promised wonders was carried out. It was nothing more than paranoid delusions; however, the impression it caused was very strong and the media impact aroused aversion and led to general euphoria. We cannot distance ourselves from the great issue that the evolution of thought and technological tools not only provided the possibility of producing new tools, but also gave rise to the broad need for new technical and didactic instruments so that it could persist in its linear development process. With this, it follows that *knowledge produces the need for knowledge*.

However, everything has its own limit, and for modern information and communication technologies, this point occurs when productions cease to be monopolies and become popular and reach the general population. Once the subject and its content are mastered, even if only partially, they realize that it is not something extreme or outside of objective reality, and that its power does not exceed the human capacity to feed its most pressing sources. In other words,

human resources represent the intrinsic and extrinsic limits of the most powerful technologies. This is not a paradox, it is a paradigm!

With the advent of ICTs, the possibility of having access to the greatest classics ever produced by and for humanity, in their original versions and languages, without being subject to the obstacle of distortion that translation causes, becomes a simple reality; however, if the habit of reading is not fostered in individuals, this becomes a harmless condition with no meaning or reason for being.

It can be seen, therefore, that mass information technology has had its design [*subtly*] modified into a *technology of mass alienation* . However, we cannot lose sight of the fact that it has served to overcome barriers that were previously unimaginable by our ancestors from eras considered highly evolved and classical. And where does the teacher fit into this new paradigm? According to recent studies, there are teachers and schools that are unable to connect these instruments to regular activities . Within this paradigm, the question arises as to whether the classroom can still be considered a [*unique*] privileged space for learning in advanced societies where new social technologies of communication and information dominate?

The education of any individual, to live and be capable of acting in the knowledge society, can no longer be thought of as something that happens only within the school environment. It is essential *to* understand learning as a continuous activity, extending throughout life, always based on the condition of broad access to experience. The analysis of learning processes in the different periods of life shows that learning as the construction of knowledge occurs from birth to the last moment of life , as long as it is interpreted as a product of experience.

Understood by experts and educators as essential and indispensable tools for well-being, new technologies are gaining effective space in classrooms. However, although many schools already have these technologies, they are not used as they should be, often being locked away in isolated rooms and out of the reach of students and teachers. It is no surprise that the introduction of new digital technologies in education has brought about changes in social, cultural and technological dynamics. Pedagogical models have been broken, becoming outdated in the face of new means of storing and disseminating information. At this time, the content, systems, values, skills, performances and abilities that are socially considered fundamental elements for human development are also changing.

With regard to technology, students cannot be left without the use and consumption of everything that can be found on the Internet, because even the most prepared scientist, if left to his own devices, without guidance, will do things that go against the expectations of erudite

sciences and even technical-technological-scientific advances, which goes against one of the pillars of formal education, which is to promote the training of an individual to be more, to be autonomous; however, one may ask: how can someone want to be more and overcome life's challenges if they do not have mastery of a professional technique that enables them to position themselves and be at a level to meet the demands of the world and the market?

In this sense, Blikstein & Zufo (2010) argue that,

In recent years, many professions have been seduced by the enchanting melodies of new communication and information technologies. In the early years of the [*now gone*] 1990s, it was the IT professionals who were fascinated by the prospects of instant wealth and the undoubted aura of wisdom. After [*this wave*], it was the turn of e-commerce and the *new economy* , which inspired the dreams of executives and administrators and promised a complete transformation of the business world. Later came the time of electronic journalism, the elimination of paper, the personalization of news, and real-time delivery. Everyone would receive only the news that interested them, every morning, without having to search for it on pages and pages of paper. IT professionals, e-commerce specialists, and *web* journalists, each in their own time, had their moment of glory, of exposure, of magical wisdom (Idem, 2010, p. 14).

Everything that was said above was nothing more than a fantasy and a hallucination; because everything in life has a cost and this individualized selection of things, messages and other nonsense would have a cost that would be beyond anyone's budget, because as already mentioned, computers and electronic media only follow certain standards, previously organized by some human who becomes capable of carrying out such procedures. They do not perform magic; they do not solve human problems, neither of high, medium or low complexity, if they were to require the formatting of ideas and connections in separate ways until reaching the ultimate purpose.

This is a principle that should be taught to all students in schools when they begin their studies and decide to delve deeper into the erudite, systematic and pragmatic fields of ICTs. Therefore, it is important to understand that they mark a very specific time and space; however, they do not replace the most rudimentary principles of human existence, which is marked by the continuous exercise of thought, from the simplest to the most complex, all of which follow a deliberate will, an autonomous desire. All of this is human action, the product of pure and constant action of human thought applied to the target object of investigation, understanding, further, that,

The great revolution that the computer promotes is [*nothing more than*] allowing for mass education in the sense that there is a lot of information available and, paradoxically, at the same time, individualized. As the years go

by, what will happen is that teaching will no longer be limited to textbooks. Books will be better, more in-depth and even more suited to computers, even with suggestions for websites and activities. Expository classes, paper, field research, combined with laboratory work, and web searches are complementary resources that must be used in an integrated and intelligent manner. Exactly the opposite of what has been done in conventional education, which wastes the most precious of all resources... the teacher, making him a mere provider of information, when he should *be* an organizer of learning situations (Moita, 1992, p. 67).

Understood in this singular way, technology in the educational field is linked to teaching, about which little or very little can be done, and to learning, which is also linked to very peculiar situations, such as the student's willingness and conditions to learn. Numerous variables will be present in the process as the teacher begins to carry out his/her praxis. Many of these variables only emerge long after the teacher is confronted with his/her target object, when he/she has the opportunity to learn more about the characteristics of this object, especially its psychology.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The insertion of a certain technology into everyday life does not always make life easier for the user, especially because its intention is to expand the user's production capacity and in educational sciences, the proposal is to provide a wider range of contact for the student with new subjects and with which, without this tool, hypothetically he would not be able to have broad visual access, *for example*, to certain technical-scientific procedures.

In the field of education, the arrival of ICTs and their insertion in this development space has awakened the possibility of behavioral changes in the ways of teaching and learning. From the understanding of this issue, transformations in pedagogical practice become possible; however, they cannot be mandatory, as something imposed, disregarding all the nuances that involve the object of teaching and learning and their respective psychological aspects. It is up to scientific research to develop new teaching methods and validate them as to their efficiency, making them available to basic education professionals.

It is important to understand and clarify that the inclusion of ICTs in education does not reduce or facilitate the conditions for studying. On the contrary, it makes the need for studying much greater, because the greater the individual access to information, the greater the demand for analysis of the same. The problem has been that we do not know where or who gave birth to the most ridiculous idea of this historical moment came from, that with the introduction of

ICTs into the system of social life, this, in itself, is capable of transforming a human being into a super genius from birth.

REFERENCES

BLIKSTEIN, Paulo; ZUFFO Marcelo Knörich . *The Sirens of Electronic Education*. São Paulo: Edusp, 2010.

MOITA, Maria da Conceição. Training and transformation paths. *In: NÓVOA, António (Org.). Teachers' Lives* . Portugal: Porto, 1992.

NIETZSCHE, FW *The Gay Science*. New York: Routledge, 2006.